

MODERN METHODS OF TREATMENT OF DENTAL DISEASES IN CHEMICAL INDUSTRY WORKERS

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Annotation. Examination of patients-it sets itself the goal of choosing treatment methods by correctly diagnosing their diseases. Examination maboynida should take a very careful approach to a change in the stream observed in the body of the patient. Because this condition can help determine the etiological factors of common and dental diseases observed in the body. One of the main conditions for examining patients is the study of their complaints. The study of the complaint of patients is distinguished from the main stages of diagnosis of the disease.

key otters: industrial corrals, dental diseases, oil, gas, oral cavity

But to accurately diagnose the disease and choose the right treatment measures will have to take into account my general state in the patient's body.

Therefore, when making a diagnosis, the methods of collecting general and special anamnestic data differ.

"Navoiyozot" helps to determine the extent to which common diseases in the body of oral diseases occur among employees of the enterprise affect the organs of the oral cavity. Because changes in the oral cavity can be namayon as one waist of the total comorbidities observed in the patient's body. In addition, the identification of General diseases in the patient's body will help me determine the indications and contraindications for the selection of anesthetics used in maxillary anesthetics, which the patient is planning to transfer to the patient.

And the collection of special Anamnesis sets itself the goal of studying the complaints of patients that belong to the facial jaw. This involves telling patients about their complaints, and additional questions are asked in order to know when they appeared, the cause and the characteristics of the discord.

One of the main reasons for the appeal of patients to the doctor – dentist khuzuri is pain. There may be pain: in dental diseases (caries, nocarious lesions, pulpitis, periodontitis), paradont (gingivitis, periodontitis, periodontoz) and oral mucosa (stomatitis) Sox, as well as pain can occur in the face – jaw.

In dental caries and nocariosis, there is pain in the tooth socket due to external influences (mechanical, thermal, and chemical), and the pain stops when the effect is over.

In pulpitis, pain is complained of for no reason, pain that occurs at night and worsens under the influence of external influences.

In the case of periodontitis, however, pain is complained of continuously, pain that hurts with a bite and worsens when bitten.

In the case of Parodont diseases, patients complain of bleeding gums in addition to pain, twitching of teeth and, in some cases, tooth decay.

In diseases of the oral mucosa, patients complain of dry mouth, redness of the mucous membrane and the appearance of wounds, as well as unpleasant odor from the mouth.

1,470 patients aged 19-55 years and older who were treated were examined for oral diseases found among employees of the Navoiazot enterprise. Patients aged 19 to 55 years and older were considered to have a higher risk of chemical production poisoning. The age levels of patients are compiled according to the WHO classification (Table 1). The age group from 19 to 29 was made up of 568 patients (38.6%), the age group from 30-39 was made up of 354 patients (24.1%), 450 patients were in the 40-54 age range (30.6%), and 98 patients were 55 years of age or older (6.67%).

Table 1.

Age levels of patients when examined by employees of the enterprise "Navoiazot"

Eat	Research methods			
	Main		Control	
	Number of patients	%	Number of patients	%
19-29 years	568	38,6	86	53,75
30-39 years	354	24,1	42	26,25
40-54 years	450	30,6	22	13,75
55 over age	98	6,67	10	6,25
Жами	1470	100	160	100

The average age of patients is 30±39 years. From the cited data (Table 1), it can be seen that patients with oral diseases found among employees of the Enterprise "Navoiazot" were 1,470 patients between the ages of 19-55 years and

older (90.1%). The control group became compatible with the core group by age.

An analysis of the sex of patients revealed what the ratio of male and female patients was

The inspection begins with the elimination of jobs in the chemical industry and cocktail conditions in the Czechs from a sanitary and hygienic device. To do this, the results of the examination, which will be carried out in a scheduled Year by the employees of the sanitary and epidemiological Control Center at the site, will be studied. Then the oral cavity of workers with all kinds of diseases is destroyed and the face-jaw is destroyed. In this case, special and additional examination methods are carried out in the ham, in which changes in the mucous membrane of the oral cavity , parodont, lip, lunge sacs are detected, hearing complaints from patients.

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